

MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract: *In this article, as a result of the application of modern approaches and innovative methods in teaching English in primary school, students develop logical thinking skills, fluency of speech, the formation of quick and correct response skills, arousal of knowledge, information about the desire to prepare thoroughly for lessons.*

Key words: *modern, innovation, elementary, play, educational, educational.*

In teaching foreign languages to students in primary school, especially in the first grade, it is necessary to take into account the age, physiological, psychological characteristics of the student. As noted in the resolution, the implementation of foreign language teaching in the form of play-style lessons and oral speech lessons in the first grades is indeed appropriate for younger students. The use of game technology in education is one of the most effective tools. During the game, their thinking, worldview, thinking expands. Scientists believe that a play-based approach to education facilitates the learning process. Not only does it make it easier, but it also increases the child's interest in science and encourages the child to gain in-depth knowledge. Play-style lessons help children develop oral speech.

First graders love a variety of pictures or videos. Through different colored pictures, games should be used regularly to enhance their speech. For example, what is this? Who is this? Who knows a lot of words? ” games such as During the game, children should be encouraged to remember words and pronounce them correctly. As children's vocabulary increases, other types of games, as well as the organization of various competitions, are also important. Games can be used by children to complete exercises on topics such as Fruit Names, Professions, and Home Appliances. Then, when they are displayed in accordance with the colorful images on the computer, students' speech develops and their range of attitudes to the environment expands. During the presentation of a new topic, words and pictures will appear on the screen. Students will be able to listen to words and pronounce them. The principle of individualization of education should be taken into account when presenting the topic on a computer. Some students have difficulty perceiving a graphic word and some a sound image. The computer helps students to identify and overcome difficulties in learning English by overcoming this or that difficulty through exercises.

It is also possible to organize other educational games aimed at mastering grammar from the second grade. For example, interesting games such as "Who is literate?", "Who is smart?", "Who am I?", "Chain", "Role play", "Find the word". “Who is smart? “The game gives good results in increasing spelling literacy. In this case, 5-6 words are written on cardboard, and the words are written correctly and incorrectly. Students are asked to find the misspelled word and spell it correctly. The winner of the game is determined by which student spells the misspelled words correctly and first.

Pronunciation is important at the beginning. According to Harmer, the first requirement for those who know their native language during the conversation is

pronunciation. At the beginning of the learning process, the teacher should focus on the student's pronunciation. Although grammar and vocabulary are important, it is useless if the speaker mispronounces them. Native speakers can also understand speech with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly.[3] Therefore, in teaching, the emphasis is first on pronunciation. In this case, the use of different audios of native speakers gives good results. The teacher should teach the correct pronunciation of letters and words during the lesson.

We know that in the current educational process, the student must be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach independent thinking. Today, English language teachers in the United States, based on the experience of English educators, use the following innovative methods.

“Merry riddles” Teach students puzzles. It is important in teaching English that they learn words that are unfamiliar to them and find the answer to the riddle. Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. (Warm-up exercises) Use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson. Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises. The A chain story method helps students to improve their speaking and memory. Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. zaki helps in the development of speech, for which it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic. Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students, allowing all students to attend class at the same time, which saves time.

In the "Find the place of the word" game, the words are swapped and the sentence is formed by putting the words in the right place. The “Collection” game is held to reinforce students' knowledge of a specific topic. The game is organized in the

form of a row competition or work in small groups. For example, groups are given a task to find the words that represent the sign. The team that finds the most points in the allotted time wins. Cartoons. Although children do not understand the words in the cartoon while learning a foreign language, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn a language. Children are taught everything from English songs to poems and stories and videos.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in teaching English, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, their interest in learning a foreign language, the development of modern didactic developments based on pedagogical technologies that help to fully meet the needs. and developing a robust mechanism for their implementation will provide a practical solution to the problem. Adequate attention should be paid to the development of speaking skills and social resilience in training. In addition, the success of any lesson in education depends in many ways on the proper organization of the lesson.

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